

Biochar and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart
Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

About the Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Cover photos: Biochar application at the Michigan State University Tree Research Center (top, D. Warnick); scanning electron micrographs of biochar taken after 3 y. in the field (bottom, J. Nash and MSU Center for Advanced Microscopy)

Table of Contents

BIOCHAR AND CLIMATE OUTCOMES: LITERATURE REVIEW AND TECHNICAL GUIDANCE	0
ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES	1
INTRODUCTION	4
WHAT IS BIOCHAR?	4
HOW CAN BIOCHAR HELP MITIGATE CLIMATE CHANGE?.....	4
FACTORS TO CONSIDER WHEN APPLYING BIOCHAR FOR SOIL C ACCRUAL, GHG EMISSION REDUCTIONS & IMPROVING CROP YIELDS	5
BIOCHAR FEEDSTOCK TYPE	5
SOIL PROPERTIES INTERACTIONS WITH BIOCHAR	7
CLIMATE	12
CROPPING SYSTEM	13
FERTILIZER USE AND NITROGEN EMISSIONS	13
BIOCHAR CHARACTERISTICS TO CONSIDER AND IMPACTS OF APPLICATION RATES.....	14
MIXING BIOCHAR WITH COMPOST	15
MICROBIAL ACTIVITY.....	15
APPLICATION INFORMATION AND OUTCOMES	17
HOW TO CHOOSE A BIOCHAR TYPE	17
HOW MUCH BIOCHAR TO APPLY	19
SUMMARY	19
REFERENCES.....	20

Introduction

WHAT IS BIOCHAR?

Biochar is a charcoal-like byproduct of the anoxic, thermochemical conversion of biomass. Biochar is composed of organic carbon (C) in a form that is very stable, i.e. not easily decomposed, such that biochar C can persist in soils for centuries, if not millennia (Lehmann et al., 2021). There is no one material or one set of defining characteristics that represents biochar. Instead, each biochar has unique physical and chemical characteristics, depending on the type of feedstock used, the production (pyrolysis) process and storage conditions. Due to widely varying combinations of different feedstocks, highest treatment temperature (HTT), duration at HTT, and oxygen concentrations, biochars can be produced with a wide range of properties (Joseph et al., 2021). However, with more than 5400 studies of biochar properties available, some strongly supported generalizations can be made about biochars, based on feedstock and production temperature, to help producers select an appropriate biochar for their needs (Ippolito et al., 2020). For example, woody feedstock biochars have the greatest surface area, while grass (straw) feedstock biochars have greater cation exchange capacity (CEC) and manure biochars have the greatest N and P contents. Biochars can also be categorized by production temperature, which generally ranges from 350-700°C. In general, biochars produced at relatively low HTT, with relatively short times at the HTT, have highly reactive surfaces and have shorter life spans in the soil, while biochars produced at > 500°C are the most persistent and have higher ash content and the highest pH. Because of the variety of characteristics available from biochar, the potential uses and positive outcomes of biochar as a soil C amendment are numerous and adaptable.

HOW CAN BIOCHAR HELP MITIGATE CLIMATE CHANGE?

The production of biochar is a climate change mitigation strategy because it converts biomass C that would otherwise decompose and be mineralized to CO₂ within a couple decades at most to a much longer-lived form of C. Biochar C persists in soils on very long time-scales, being very slowly and only partially converted to CO₂. The most famous example of this are the terra preta soils discovered in the Amazon that were created by indigenous people adding low temperature wood charcoal to soils over 2000 years ago (Glaser et al., 2002). In addition to locking up C in soils, biochar can contribute to climate change mitigation through multiple other mechanisms (Lehmann et al., 2021). When used as an agricultural amendment, it can increase nutrient availability (i.e. soil fertility). Increases in soil fertility, as well as increased water holding capacity and reductions in or buffering of soil pH with biochar improve plant productivity, which further draws down atmospheric CO₂, contributing to climate change mitigation (Luo et al., 2023). Globally, crop responses to biochar are generally positive, with average increases in yields of 9-16% (He et al., 2024; Lehmann et al., 2021). Biochar has also been shown to decrease nutrient losses via leaching, and thus decrease the need for fertilization, reducing soil GHG emissions attributed to fertilizer production and application (Lehman et al., 2021). In a recent meta-analysis, biochar is shown to reduce all GHG emissions, including CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O emissions by 4.8%, 2.8%, and 37.0% respectively (He et al., 2024). The significant reduction in N₂O observed across most soils and cropping systems presents the best climate change mitigation potential for biochar, as N₂O has 300x's the global warming potential (GWP) of CO₂. In fact, the calculated reduction in the total GWP, which considers and weights reductions in CO₂, N₂O and CH₄, has been estimated to be 684.25 Tg

CO₂eq year⁻¹ in meta-analyses of published literature (He et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024). That is in comparison to average increases in soil organic C stocks with biochar of 29%, or in the top 20 cm of soil, 13 Mg C ha⁻¹ (Gross et al., 2021).

Overall, we have made very good research progress over the last few decades, with over 100 published meta-analyses and reviews of biochar research published in just the last ten years. We now have the critical knowledge needed to make predictions about how specific soils will interact with specific biochars, based on the chemical properties and production conditions (He et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2023; Lehman et al., 2021; Woolf et al., 2021; Dokoohaki et al., 2019). There is even a comprehensive review describing under which conditions biochar can have detrimental effects (Brtnicky et al., 2021). We are now positioned better than ever to use biochar as a climate change mitigation, soil health improvement and yield enhancer, with models currently available to predict biochar properties from feedstock and production conditions, to assess biochar as part of GHG inventories, and to complete system life cycle assessments (LCAs; Singh et al., 2024; Woolf et al., 2021; Lehman et al., 2021; Woolf et al., 2016). For example, we can predict the C content of biochar, which varies with feedstock and production conditions from as low as 7% (gasification of biosolids) to 79% (pyrolysis of wood at above 600°C). Further, models predict that of initial biochar C additions to soils, 63–82% will remain unmineralized in soil after 100 years at the global mean annual cropland-temperature of 14.9°C (Woolf et al., 2021). These predictions have found entrance to IPCC's guidelines for national GHG accounting (Ogle et al., 2019) and the voluntary C market (e.g., Carbonfuture, 2023). Biochar is a promising strategy for building soil C and reducing GHG emissions, but there is further work needed to provide local guidance for optimizing biochar use for these and a host of other potential benefits that are also very context dependent. Successful application of biochar will be accomplished with location specific information regarding suitability of biochar for building soil C and/or reducing soil GHG emissions and other benefits; regional or local tools for finding and selecting appropriate biochar products; local guidance for application rates and methods; standardization of production and marketing practices; and long-term LCAs.

Factors to consider when applying biochar for soil C accrual, GHG emission reductions & improving crop yields

BIOCHAR FEEDSTOCK TYPE

The impact of biochar on GHG emissions is closely related to the type of biomass used as feedstock. In general biochar derived from wood or herbaceous biomass tends to increase soil N₂O emissions, while biochar produced from manure, biosolids/biowaste, and lignocellulosic materials either reduces emissions or has no significant effect (Zhang et al., 2024; Kaur et al., 2023; Atilano-Camino et al., 2022). Similarly, CO₂ emissions have been found to be higher with straw and manure based biochars, whereas grass-derived biochar has shown the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions while biochar produced from wood and other waste residues has no significant impact on soil CO₂ fluxes (Atilano-Camino et al., 2022). Lignocellulosic material had the highest GWP potential compared to wood and herbaceous (Shakoor et al., 2021). Biochar derived from straw waste and crop residue lowered GWP by 26% and

16% respectively, GHGI by 35% and 18% respectively, and increased crop yields by 21% and 18% respectively (Zhang et al., 2020). Kerner et al., 2023 reported that biochar derived from lignocellulose or agricultural biomass can better inhibit N₂O through modulating denitrification genes *nirS* and *nosZ*; repeated biochar amendment may be needed as inhibition is stronger in shorter durations. He et al., 2024 reported an increase in CO₂ emissions when wood-biochar was applied at rates exceeding 40-60t/ha/year.

However, the climate change mitigation potential of biochar extends beyond its immediate effect on soil GHG emissions. The primary source of mitigation from biochar is the delayed decomposition of the feedstock: transforming organic material into biochar can stabilize carbon that would otherwise decay, emitting CO₂ in the process. As such, it is important to consider alternative uses (i.e., the counterfactual use) of biochar feedstock sources. This could impact both overall GHG mitigation and also impact soil health.

Important considerations on feedstock sourcing, alternative feedstock uses, and GHG implications:

- If biochar is made from a persistent material that would not have decomposed within coming decades (e.g., trees that may have continued to grow, or dead wood that wouldn't decompose quickly), the benefit of "locking up" that carbon in biochar is relatively small and might not be outweighed by the GHG emissions used to collect the material and process it.
- Competition or competing uses of feedstocks can have important implications for GHG mitigation potential. For instance, there are potential cases where biomass used for biochar could have been used to produce energy directly that would replace energy generation from high GHG intensity sources such as coal (e.g., direct combustion for bioenergy which represents a cleaner form of energy compared to fossil fuels). Therefore, when considering the overall climate impact of a biochar system, it is important to consider the counterfactual in full, including the fate of the intended feedstock material and the impact of the biochar generation process (Matuščík, Pohořelý, and Kočí 2022).
- If the existing energy system is largely fossil fuel-based, then direct biomass combustion may have a higher climate mitigation potential than biochar production since bioenergy would be replacing some proportion of fossil fuels.
- There seems to be general agreement that as the energy mix becomes greener and more renewable, the climate mitigation potential of biochar goes up and producing biochar becomes increasingly favorable compared to using biomass to generate energy.
- From [Carbon Plan](#): "If a biomass feedstock currently serves a function that will need to be replaced if the feedstock is used for CDR, any emissions associated with the replacement must be considered. For example, if agricultural waste is currently used as animal feed or left on the fields to contribute to nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in soils, using that agricultural waste for CDR could result in new demand for feed or fertilizer, respectively."
- In some cases, feedstocks may be grown for the sole purpose of biochar production (purpose-grown feedstocks). In these cases, it is critical to ensure that purpose grown feedstock is sustainably cultivated on marginal lands and does not compete with food production systems.

Important considerations for soil health, soil organic carbon and GHGs given potential use of crop residues and stover removal for biochar production:

- From a soil health perspective, removing stover or other crop residues can have important implications. Feedstocks incorporating crop residues that would have normally been applied to fields but are instead converted to biochar could result in nutrient value loss. There are similar concerns for animal waste converted to biochar (Ghodake et al. 2021).
- Crop residue management and retention can help promote and maintain soil health and soil organic carbon stocks (Sarkar et al. 2020).
- Majumder et al., (2019) performed a literature review that explores what happens to soil carbon stocks when residues are retained versus when they are turned into biochar: the transformation of crop residues into biochar may promote longer-term carbon storage but may present economic tradeoffs in certain systems (i.e., smallholder) where the availability of crop residues presents an economical way to promote soil health and fertility (Majumder et al. 2019).
- Johnson et al. (2014) explores the question of how much residue retention for corn stover is necessary to maintain SOC levels. They use deltaSOC data and residue retention rates across a number of sites to derive an empirical relationship and find, on average, keeping about 6 Mg residue ha⁻¹yr⁻¹ maybe a useful generic rate as a point of discussion. However, the authors caution against the universality of this rate as context will matter and it is impossible to predict for any one field.
- Jin et al. (2014) explored emissions of CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ in different residue management treatments and found, on average across sites, that stover removal does decrease emissions of N₂O and CO₂; however, this study does not include changes in SOC stocks and so we cannot draw conclusions about net mitigation effects.
- Xu et al. (2019) performed a meta-analysis on the effects of stover removal on SOC and found that “stover removal generally reduced final SOC stocks by 8% in the upper 0–15 or 0–30 cm, compared to stover retained, irrespective of soil properties and tillage practices. Moderate rates of removal (50%) can still lead to increases in SOC albeit lower rates than full retention.

Important LCA considerations:

- If biochar production is done in an inefficient way that uses significant amounts of energy, produces high GHG emissions, and doesn't produce any energy as a by-product, the production process might represent a net increase in GHG emissions compared to the counterfactual.

SOIL PROPERTIES INTERACTIONS WITH BIOCHAR

1. SOIL PH

Soil pH mediates the potential of biochar to act as a climate change mitigator, is an important property to consider when selecting a biochar and is a soil property that can be adjusted or optimized with biochar application. Soil pH interacts with biochar to play a crucial role in regulating GHG emissions, but effects are highly context dependent. In general, N₂O emissions after biochar application tend to be greater in acidic (pH <6) and alkaline (pH >8) soils, while soils with a neutral pH (6 < pH ≤ 8) exhibit lower emissions (Zhang et al., 2024; Kaur et al., 2023). Atilano-Camino et al. (2022) reported that strongly acidic soils (pH <4.5) and neutral soils (pH 6.6–7.5) showed a reduction in N₂O emissions with biochar, whereas emissions under moderately acidic and alkaline conditions were not significantly affected. Soil respiration (CO₂ emission) is generally also greater as microbial activity tends to be stimulated by biochar application (Rasul et al., 2022; Ding et al., 2017) and this has been demonstrated in acidic soils

with an initial soil pH of 4.5–6.5 (Atilano-Camino et al., 2022) as well as neutral and alkaline soils (Zhang et al., 2020). Biochar application in acidic soil (pH < 5.5) can also reduce CH₄ emissions by 25%. In weakly acidic soils (pH 5.5–6.5), neutral soils (pH 6.5–7.5), and alkaline soils (pH > 7.5), CH₄ emissions are shown to increase by 11–30%. While these findings suggest a relationship between soil pH and GHG emissions with biochar, the overall effect is highly dependent on other soil properties and environmental conditions. It is also important to remember that in general, soil GHG emissions are reduced with biochar application compared to soils with no biochar. Given the variability in reported outcomes, soil pH should be considered when selecting biochar applications, but it may not be the most reliable property for assessing biochar's climate change mitigation potential in a specific system.

Beyond climate change mitigation, biochar can also play a major role in improving other soil properties of acidic soils, alkaline soils, and saline-alkaline soils. Recent studies highlight biochar's effectiveness in mitigating soil acidity and improving saline-alkali soils. In highly acidic soils, which contain toxic levels of aluminum (Al³⁺) and manganese (Mn²⁺), and are deficient in essential nutrients like phosphorus, potassium, and calcium (Tusar et al., 2023), biochar can provide significant improvement in nutrient provisioning and soil quality through several mechanisms. First, biochar has a pH neutralizing effect because most biochars are alkaline, due to carbonates and oxides formed during pyrolysis, which results in an increase in soil pH as H⁺ ions are neutralized (Bolan et al., 2023; Ghorbani et al., 2024). Second, many biochars have relatively high cation exchange capacities (CEC) such that toxic Al³⁺ and H⁺ are adsorbed and Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ are retained (Bedassa et al., 2020; Ghorbani et al., 2024). Finally, in the long-term and unlike lime (CaCO₃), biochar increases soil organic matter, base saturation and effective CEC (Chintala et al., 2013).

A global meta-analysis (Zhang et al., 2025) confirmed biochar's effectiveness in raising acidic soil pH, and Tusar et al. (2023) found the highest pH increase (~4.78 units) occurs in strongly acidic soils (pH < 4), supporting biochar's strong buffering capacity. Multiple field studies also show biochar's benefits in acidic soils for crop yields and in fact a global analysis shows increases in crop yields are particularly pronounced in acidic soils (Lehmann et al., 2021). For example, biochar applied at 15 t/ha with NPK and poultry manure increased crop yield of a leafy vegetable (*Amaranthus*) by 54% in strongly acidic soils (Elias et al., 2020). In another study, combining rice husk biochar with lime increased phosphorus availability by 137% and improved maize yield by 78% (Mehnaz et al., 2021). If raising pH in an acidic soil is goal for biochar application, look for a biochar product that reports the liming equivalent or send a sample to a lab for this analysis.

Despite broad guidelines discouraging biochar application in soils with pH > 7.5, recent studies show biochar has potential for also buffering alkaline soils, while also providing salinity mitigation and enhancing fertility. In a global meta-analysis synthesizing data from 137 studies and 1,447 datasets, Mao et al. (2024) demonstrates the efficacy of biochar in reclamation of saline-alkaline soils. This analysis shows that when added to alkaline and saline soils, biochar can significantly reduce the sodium adsorption ratio, on average by 30% and reduce the Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP) by 29%. In addition CEC was increased on average by 49% with additional benefits including lowered bulk density, increased porosity and soil water retention. In alkaline and saline soils, biochar produced at 400–500°C was most effective. In mildly saline soils (<0.4% salinity, water-surplus regions) 41–80 t ha⁻¹ of neutral biochar (pH 6–8) was beneficial, while in highly saline soils (>0.4% salinity, water-deficit regions) >80 t ha⁻¹ of acidic biochar (pH ≤ 6) was optimal. It has also been shown that biochar produced from agricultural residues was particularly effective in reclaiming highly alkaline soils. For example, Liang et al. (2021) found that Palmetto branch-derived biochar (pH 5.6, 500–600°C, anoxic conditions) improved soil

porosity, bulk density, and water availability in soils with pH >8.5; however, excessive application negatively affected hydraulic properties, with 21.9 t ha⁻¹ identified as optimal. Chen et al. (2024) reported that maize straw biochar (pH 8.92, carbonized at 350°C for 40 minutes) increased soil water content, reduced salinity indicators (EC, Na⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, SAR), and enhanced enzyme activity, improving maize growth, with a ~3% biochar application rate being most effective for reducing salinity and enhancing crop performance. When applying biochar, keep in mind that biochar's pH can be modified through low-temperature pyrolysis, hydrolysis, acidification, oxidation, aging, or acid-binding, allowing the production of acidic biochars that can lower alkaline soil pH (Qi et al. (2024). Similarly, Sun et al. (2022) confirmed that acidic and neutral biochars effectively reduce soil alkalinity, reinforcing biochar's role in soil modification.

Finally, when it comes to increasing SOC stocks in both acidic and alkaline soils, Gross et al., (2021) reported that biochar remains stable and contributes to SOC accumulation. Overall, this review found that SOC increases in neutral soils (pH 6.5–7.5) on average by 19.4 Mg ha⁻¹ SOC (a 42% increase) and in alkaline soils (pH >7.5) by 12.8 Mg ha⁻¹ SOC (a 34% increase). Surprisingly, SOC gains in alkaline soils (8.1 g kg⁻¹, 117%) exceeded those in acidic soils (4.1 g kg⁻¹, 57%) likely due to greater biochar stability in neutral and alkaline soils compared to acidic soils. Biochar degrades faster in acidic soils due to a stronger priming effect and enhanced native SOC mineralization. In addition, higher Ca²⁺ levels in alkaline soils promote mineral-organic complex formation, stabilizing biochar and enhancing SOC retention. Overall, it is important to not exclude alkaline soils from biochar application as there are a number of very positive benefits when the optimal biochar is selected.

2. SOIL CARBON CONTENT

Although SOC accrual is a desired outcome of biochar application, the potential for SOC accrual with biochar and is impacted by extant SOC stocks. Although we tend to think of biochar as a successful soil C building strategy only in soils with initially low SOC stocks, research shows that biochar can effectively build SOC in soils with relatively high amounts of SOC. A global meta-analysis by Gross et al. (2021), synthesizing 64 studies with 736 data points, found that the most significant SOC increases occurred in soils already rich in SOC (>2%). We also find that soil GHG emissions in response to biochar depend on extant SOC. In response to biochar application, soil N₂O emissions were generally lower in soils with moderate SOC levels (10 < SOC ≤ 20 g kg⁻¹) (Zhang et al., 2024; Kaur et al., 2023). He et al. (2024) found that N₂O emissions initially increased with SOC levels but decreased with higher biochar application rates. Bai et al. (2025) reported that soils with medium and high SOC had significantly reduced CH₄ emissions, 12.9% and 12%, respectively with biochar. The impact of biochar on CO₂ emissions varies with SOC content, with reduced CO₂ emissions (8.6%) in low-SOC soils but increased CO₂ emissions (8.5%) in medium-SOC soils.

Biochar plays a role in SOC stabilization (non-biochar SOC), soil structure improvement, nutrient retention, microbial activity enhancement, and erosion resistance, regardless of initial SOC levels, which has a positive feedback to climate change mitigation. For instance, Nyambo et al. (2018) studied maize residue biochar produced at 500°C for 4 hours, applied at 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% (w/w) to an acidic Hutton soil (initial SOC: 2.2%). After 140 days, biochar application increased SOC from 2.2% to 2.34%, alongside improvements in microbial biomass carbon (496 to 1615 mg/kg); soil aggregation (mean weight diameter of 0.58 mm to 0.70 mm); and erosion control (soil loss reduction of 27% to 70%). These enhancements were directly proportional to biochar application rates, with the highest benefits

observed at 10% biochar application. Overall, these findings reaffirm biochar's broad applicability across diverse soil conditions, promoting long-term soil health and sustainability, irrespective of SOC levels.

3. SOIL CATION EXCHANGE CAPACITY

Beyond climate change mitigation, biochar plays a crucial role in enhancing soil physicochemical and biological properties. Recent studies highlight biochar's potential to improve cation exchange capacity (CEC) across various soil types, challenging the assumption that soils with CEC > 12 meq/100g (0–30 cm) are less suited for biochar application. Soil GHG emissions are in part controlled by interactions between biochar and CEC. In response to biochar application, soil N₂O emissions are generally reduced in soils with moderate (10 < CEC ≤ 20 cmol kg⁻¹) or low (≤ 10 cmol kg⁻¹) CEC (Zhang et al., 2024), while, CO₂ emissions increase with increasing soil CEC (0–60 cmol kg⁻¹), and CH₄ and N₂O emissions decrease as CEC increases (He et al., 2024).

Research also indicates that biochar's influence on CEC varies with soil properties and application rates. For instance, Hailegnaw et al. (2019) conducted a 12-week incubation study using 10 soils with CEC ranging from 4.5 to 35.6 meq/100g and pH values between 4.50 and 7.10. Coniferous wood chip biochar, produced via fast pyrolysis at 700°C, was applied at 0.5%, 2%, 4%, and 8% (w/w). Soils with CEC < 20 meq/100g and pH ≤ 6.2 showed up to a 35.4% increase in CEC and a pH rise of up to 1.17 units, with the 4% and 8% biochar rates proving most effective. However, in high-CEC soils (> 20 meq/100g) with high exchangeable Ca²⁺ content, CEC declined, highlighting soil-specific interactions. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Dai et al. (2020), synthesizing 1254 paired comparisons from 153 studies, categorized soils based on CEC levels. The results showed that low-CEC soils (<10 meq/100g) experienced the highest increases in crop productivity following biochar application, while medium-CEC soils (10–20 meq/100g) also benefited, though to a lesser extent. In contrast, high-CEC soils (>20 meq/100g) showed no significant impact on productivity. These findings suggest that while biochar is particularly beneficial for low-CEC soils, soils with CEC up to 20 meq/100g can also experience notable improvements. A deeper understanding of these soil-specific interactions can help refine biochar application strategies to align with the latest scientific evidence.

4. SOIL PHYSICAL PROPERTIES (TEXTURE, BULK DENSITY, POROSITY, COMPACTION, WATER HOLDING CAPACITY)

4A. SOIL TEXTURE

Soil texture is an important control on soil structure and thus water and air flow in soils, which in turn plays a large role in how biochar impact soil GHG emissions. In response to biochar application, soil CO₂ emissions were generally greater in soils with higher clay content, while emissions of the GHGs N₂O and CH₄ are generally greater from silt and sandy soils (He et al., 2024). However, GHG emissions with biochar are very context dependent, with other studies reporting contrasting results. For example, Atilano-Camino et al. (2022) found that soil CO₂ emissions were greater in fine and coarse textured soils, while Zhang et al. (2024) found that soil N₂O emissions were generally reduced in medium and coarse textured soils. Furthermore, Zhang et al (2020) found that soil N₂O and CO₂ emissions were highest in sandy soils (44% and 25% respectively) compared to clayey and loamy while loamy soil and clayey soil saw a higher increase in CH₄ emissions (10% and 12%, respectively) compared to sandy soil (5%). Bai et al., (2025) reported that medium-textured soils showed a 4.4 % increase in CO₂ emissions. Medium and coarse-textured soils showed 10 % and 19.5 % reduction in N₂O emissions. Fine-textured soils exhibited

a 60 % increase in CH₄ emissions, while coarse-textured soils showed 30.9 % decrease in CH₄ emissions. Although soil texture likely plays a key role in determining GHG emissions, it is very context dependent such that there are not generalizable conclusions to be drawn from the current literature. Therefore, soil texture is an important soil property to consider when choosing a biochar in general, but not an effective soil characteristic for assessing climate change mitigation potential. In contrast soil texture is a good predictor of soil C accrual with biochar application, with SOC accrual rates increasing as sand decreases and clay increases (Gross et al., 2021).

4B. WATER HOLDING CAPACITY (A.K.A. AVAILABLE WATER CAPACITY/PLANT-AVAILABLE WATER)

Biochar has demonstrated significant potential in improving soil moisture retention, even in soils with higher plant available water (PAW). Recent studies show that biochar can enhance plant-available water in these soils as well, making it a valuable amendment for a wide range of soil types. For instance, a study by Kimmo Rasa et al. (2018) observed that biochar increased PAW in heavy clay soil with an initial PAW of 0.3 cm/cm, showing a 17% increase in homogenized soil (PAW increased to 0.35 cm/cm) and a 32% increase in natural soil aggregates (from 0.22 to 0.29 cm/cm). This improvement in water retention was attributed to biochar's internal porosity, which enhanced soil moisture capacity both directly and indirectly by modifying soil texture and structure. The results of this study indicated that biochar improves water retention and plant-available water, regardless of the initial soil moisture content, ultimately helping plants better withstand moisture stress. Similarly, Jun Zhang et al. (2021) found that biochar amendments increased volumetric PAW across several soil types. In a sandy soil, a 2% biochar addition increased PAW by 57%, while in a silt loam, PAW increased by 20%, and in a clay soil, PAW improved by 2%. These findings suggest that biochar's impact on water retention varies depending on soil texture but remains beneficial in soils with both low and high PAW. These studies highlight the ability of biochar to improve soil moisture dynamics, regardless of initial water availability, underscores its broad applicability for enhancing soil moisture retention, supporting plant growth, and improving overall soil health. Therefore, biochar's role in improving PAW should be considered across a wider range of soils, with more attention given to its varied benefits based on specific soil characteristics, feedstock, pyrolysis conditions, and application rates.

4C. BULK DENSITY AND SOIL COMPACTION

Changes in soil compaction and bulk density due to biochar application can have interactive effects on GHG emissions. Notably, across all bulk density and compaction levels, biochar application reduced soil N₂O emissions across all soil types, with loose and medium bulk density soils having emissions decreased by 12.5% and 15.8%, respectively (Bai et al., 2025). In response to biochar application, more compacted soils had reduced CH₄ emissions, by 8.4%, whereas less compacted soils had significantly increased CH₄ emissions, by 30.1%. Additionally, compact soils had increased CO₂ emissions by 7.9%, while medium and loose soils had CO₂ emission reductions with application of biochars (Bai et al., 2025).

Biochar application can significantly improve soil physical properties such as bulk density and compaction. Soil compaction, often marked by an increase in bulk density, is a common challenge that negatively affects soil health and plant growth. Biochar has shown significant promise in reducing soil compaction, particularly in soils with high bulk density (greater than 1.4 g/cm³), by improving soil structure and promoting better aeration and drainage. Research indicates that the application of biochar can reduce soil compaction by 3–31%, with a more substantial impact in coarse-textured soils or sandy soils (~31% reduction) compared to finer-textured soils like clay (~9.2% reduction) (Blanco-Canqui,

2017). Biochar also has specific advantages in addressing compaction issues in flood-affected soils. Frequent flooding leads to the deposition of sand-rich sediments that can degrade soil structure, increase bulk density, and reduce water-holding capacity. Waterlogged conditions further exacerbate compaction by limiting aeration and microbial activity, but biochar's high porosity, large surface area, and capacity to improve soil aggregation and drainage can significantly mitigate these effects. Biochar's presence enhances soil aeration and moisture management, supporting healthy plant growth in flood-affected soils because biochar-amended soils drain excess water faster, improving hydraulic conductivity and altering evaporation rates, which helps prevent waterlogging and maintains healthy soil conditions. Additionally, biochar can immobilize flood-borne contaminants, including heavy metals, pesticides, and pathogens, preventing further degradation of the soil (Kumar et al., 2022). Certain types of biochar feedstocks have been found particularly beneficial for flood-affected soils (Kumar et al., 2022). Manure-based biochar, such as cow urine-enriched biochar, enhances pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and WHC, providing added resilience against flood stress. Crop residue biochar (e.g., straw-based biochar) improves porosity and nutrient retention, reducing nutrient leaching in sandy flood deposits. Hardwood biochar offers long-term stability and helps immobilize contaminants, while waste biomass biochar provides a cost-effective solution for smallholder farmers in flood-prone regions. Overall, biochar not only improves bulk density and reduces compaction but also supports the restoration of flood-damaged soils, highlighting its broad applicability as a soil amendment for enhancing soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability across various soil types.

CLIMATE

Biochar application plays a complex role in regulating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with its impact varying based on temperature and precipitation. While biochar has shown potential in mitigating GHG emissions in certain conditions, excessive application or unfavorable environmental factors can lead to unintended increases. Understanding these interactions is essential for optimizing biochar use to maximize its benefits for soil health and climate change mitigation. In response to biochar application, soil CO₂ emissions significantly increased by 15.4% in subtropical regions, whereas no impact on N₂O emissions was observed in tropical and subtropical regions. However, in temperate regions, N₂O emissions were reduced by 20.6%, while soil CH₄ emissions decreased by 24.8% and 9.2% in tropical and temperate regions, respectively (Bai et al., 2025). He et al. (2024) reported a reduction in total GHG emissions in CO₂-equivalent following the application of 0–20 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ wood biochar in temperate regions (310.50 Tg CO₂ year⁻¹), which was significantly higher than reductions observed in other regions. However, when biochar application exceeded 60 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, GHG emissions in temperate regions increased sharply, reaching 991.93 Tg CO₂ year⁻¹.

TEMPERATURE

In response to biochar application, soil N₂O emissions were generally higher when the mean annual temperature exceeded 20°C (Zhang et al., 2024; Bai et al., 2025). In contrast, soil CO₂ emissions were reduced at temperatures above 25°C, while CH₄ and N₂O emissions showed a decreasing trend as temperatures increased from 0 to 40°C (He et al., 2024).

PRECIPITATION

In response to biochar application, soil N₂O emissions were generally higher when mean annual precipitation was below 600 mm (Zhang et al., 2024). Soil CO₂ emissions increased by 10.7% in regions with mean annual precipitation of at least 1000 mm, whereas CH₄ emissions decreased by 9.7% under high precipitation conditions (Bai et al., 2025). Additionally, as annual precipitation increased from 1000 mm to 3000 mm, both CO₂ and N₂O emissions were reduced, while CH₄ emissions increased (He et al., 2024).

CROPPING SYSTEM

The impact of biochar on GHG emissions varies across different cropping systems, influencing SOC accrual and overall climate change mitigation potential. Different crop types and management practices play a crucial role in determining the extent of biochar's effectiveness in reducing emissions. A global meta-analysis by Shakoor et al. (2021) assessed the impact of four major crop types—rice, maize, wheat, and vegetables—on GHG emissions in biochar-amended soils. The study identified biochar added to vegetable systems as the most effective for CO₂ mitigation. For N₂O emissions, biochar additions to maize and rice systems exhibited significant mitigation potential, while all crop types had CH₄ reductions with biochar application. Additionally, biochar application reduced the overall global warming potential (GWP) in rice and wheat cultivation systems (Shakoor et al., 2021).

Soil N₂O emissions were shown to increase on average by ~50% in perennial cropping systems, but N₂O emissions were reduced by 30%–45% in other agronomic and horticultural systems (Borchard et al., 2019). In both diversified and monoculture cropping systems, biochar reduced N₂O emissions by 18.2% and 11%, respectively, while also lowering CH₄ emissions. However, biochar also slightly increased CO₂ emissions across all systems.

FERTILIZER USE AND NITROGEN EMISSIONS

NITROGEN FERTILIZER AND EMISSIONS

Soil N₂O emissions were lowered with N application rates >400 kg N ha⁻¹ (Zhang et al., 2024). Soil N₂O emissions were reduced by 46% when applied with mineral fertilizer [e.g. NH₄NO₃, (NH₄)₂SO₄, KNO₃]; 34% with urea and 32% for mixture of organic and mineral fertilizers (Borchard et al., 2019). Bai et al., 2025 reported that biochar when combined with low N fertilization increased N₂O, and CH₄ emissions, while it decreased when applied with high N fertilization rate or no N fertilization.

ORGANIC FERTILIZERS

Soil GHG emissions were increased when organic amendments were applied individually and/or co-applied with biochar (Fu et al., 2023). Soil N₂O emissions were reduced by ~20% when biochar was applied with organic fertilizer (Borchard et al., 2019). Bai et al., 2025 reported that biochar when applied in combination with residue or without organic fertilizer it reduced CO₂ and N₂O emissions while manure combination slightly increased CO₂ and N₂O emissions.

BIOCHAR CHARACTERISTICS TO CONSIDER AND IMPACTS OF APPLICATION RATES

The impact of biochar on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is strongly influenced by its properties, including pH, surface area, aging, pyrolysis conditions, and application rates. Biochar with a lower pH (≤ 7) and moderate BET surface area ($40\text{--}80\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) has been shown to reduce soil N_2O emissions by 30.25% (Zhang et al., 2024). In contrast, alkaline biochar ($\text{pH} > 8$) has been linked to a 19.36% increase in CO_2 emissions (Atilano-Camino et al., 2022). A global meta-analysis further reports that acidic biochar ($\text{pH} \leq 7$) mitigates N_2O emissions but enhances CH_4 emissions, whereas neutral to alkaline biochar ($\text{pH} \geq 7$) tends to increase N_2O emissions while reducing CH_4 emissions from cropland soils (Shakoor et al., 2021).

Biochar aging also plays a critical role in its effect on GHG emissions. Fresh biochar primarily mitigates N_2O emissions but increases CH_4 emissions, whereas aged biochar elevates both N_2O and CO_2 emissions while reducing CH_4 emissions (Feng et al., 2022). Biochar with a C:N ratio ≤ 50 demonstrates greater CO_2 mitigation from cropland soils. In contrast, biochar with a higher C:N ratio (> 300 and ≤ 300) significantly reduces N_2O emissions, whereas biochar with a lower C:N ratio (≤ 50 and ≤ 150) increases N_2O emissions. Additionally, biochar with a C:N ratio > 300 and ≤ 50 effectively mitigates CH_4 emissions, whereas biochar with a C:N ratio ≤ 300 and ≤ 150 marginally increases CH_4 emissions (Shakoor et al., 2021).

Pyrolysis temperature also plays a crucial role in determining biochar's impact on GHG fluxes. Biochar produced at moderate pyrolysis temperatures ($400\text{--}500^\circ\text{C}$) suppresses N_2O emissions, whereas biochar produced at lower temperatures ($200\text{--}300^\circ\text{C}$) leads to a 19.24% increase in CO_2 emissions (Zhang et al., 2024; Atilano-Camino et al., 2022). A pyrolysis temperature $\leq 500^\circ\text{C}$ has been linked to reduced global warming potential (GWP) (Shakoor et al., 2021). Biochar with a C:N ratio between $20\text{--}300$ significantly reduces N_2O emissions while increasing CO_2 emissions (Zhang et al., 2020). Additionally, biochar with $\text{pH} < 7$ and $\text{pH} > 8$ reduces N_2O emissions while increasing CH_4 emissions. CO_2 emissions increase with biochar $\text{pH} < 8$ and $\text{pH} > 10$ but slightly decrease within the pH range of $8\text{--}10$ (Zhang et al., 2020). Biochar produced at pyrolysis temperatures $> 600^\circ\text{C}$ reduces CO_2 emissions by 32% and N_2O emissions by 25%. Conversely, biochar produced at $< 600^\circ\text{C}$ significantly reduces N_2O emissions but increases CO_2 and CH_4 emissions (Zhang et al., 2020).

Biochar application rates also significantly influence its effect on GHG emissions. At lower concentrations ($\leq 5\%$), biochar can reduce N_2O emissions by up to 37.06%, whereas application rates below 10 t ha^{-1} are associated with a 23.37% increase in N_2O emissions (Atilano-Camino et al., 2022). A global meta-analysis by Shakoor et al. (2021) found that biochar application generally increases CO_2 emissions while significantly reducing CH_4 emissions, with the greatest CH_4 mitigation observed at rates exceeding 40 t ha^{-1} . Regarding N_2O emissions, application rates of ≤ 10 , ≤ 20 , and $> 40\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ increase emissions, whereas rates of $\leq 30\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ and $\leq 40\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ exhibit mitigation effects. Application rates $\leq 30\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ significantly decrease GWP (Shakoor et al., 2021). Soil CH_4 and CO_2 emissions significantly increase at application rates $< 10\text{ t ha}^{-1}$, whereas CH_4 emissions decrease at $40\text{--}80\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ and CO_2 emissions decrease at rates $> 80\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ (Zhang et al., 2020). Soil N_2O emissions are significantly reduced by $> 50\%$ at application rates $> 20\text{ Mg ha}^{-1}$ and by 20% at rates between $10\text{--}20\text{ Mg ha}^{-1}$ (Borchard et al., 2019). He et al., 2024 reported an increase in CO_2 and CH_4 emissions with biochar application rates exceeding $20\text{--}40\text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{ year}^{-1}$ while N_2O emissions increased when biochar application rates exceeded $40\text{--}60\text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{ year}^{-1}$. However, crop yields decreased significantly with biochar rates exceeding $20\text{--}40\text{ t ha}^{-1}\text{ year}^{-1}$. These

findings highlight the context-dependent nature of biochar's role in climate mitigation, emphasizing the need for careful consideration of its production conditions and field application strategies. A meta-analysis by Zhang et al. (2024) reported that biochar's potential to reduce N₂O emissions is primarily influenced by biochar pH, application rate, total carbon content, nitrogen application rate, and mean annual temperature. Another global meta-analysis by Zhang et al. (2020) found that soil pH, biochar pH, and biochar C:N ratio are the most influential factors governing soil CH₄, CO₂, and N₂O emissions, respectively.

MIXING BIOCHAR WITH COMPOST

There are three primary approaches for producing or co-applying biochar and compost: (i) **co-composted biochar**, produced by composting biochar with organic waste feedstocks; (ii) **incubated biochar-compost**, formed by incubating biochar with stabilized or mature compost over a specified period; and (iii) **biochar-compost mix**, created by simply blending biochar and compost and applying it directly to soil (Khan et al., 2023). Multiple reviews have emphasized the advantages of combining biochar and compost. A field study by Gao et al. (2022) in California assessed the effect of biochar co-compost on winter wheat in loamy soils. The biochar was produced from a woody biomass mix (Douglas fir, ponderosa pine, tree prunings, and nutshells) via pyrolysis at 900 °C, while the compost comprised dairy manure and orchard clippings. Co-composting with 1 t biochar significantly reduced nutrient leaching, especially NH₄⁺ and ortho-phosphate, and enhanced water holding capacity, resulting in improved crop growth. Another study by Ducey et al. (2021) at a Superfund site in Missouri, evaluated the co-application of compost with biochars derived from poultry litter, beef cattle manure, and lodgepole pine to restore metal-contaminated soils. Biochar (2.5% and 5%) was applied alongside compost (0%, 2.5%, and 5%), and native grasses—switchgrass and buffalograss—were planted to assess soil and plant response. Poultry litter biochar at 5% was most effective in reducing bioavailable Cd and Zn. The highest biomass yield occurred with beef cattle manure biochar (2.5%) and compost (5%). Additionally, microbial biomass and enzyme activities (e.g., β-glucosidase and esterase) peaked in treatments with poultry litter biochar and compost at 5%, indicating improved microbial functioning. We know that biochar and compost individually both improve soil health through distinct mechanisms, biochar by enhancing soil structure, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and contaminant binding, and compost by improving fertility and stimulating microbial activity. However, when combined, there are significant synergistic effects, offering a more comprehensive improvement in soil quality (Qian et al., 2023; Agegnehu et al., 2017). El-Naggar et al. (2019) further supported these findings, highlighting that co-composted biochar functions as a slow-release fertilizer that enhances nutrient availability, supports plant growth, and improves overall soil fertility. Together, these studies demonstrate that integrated biochar–compost applications not only enhance soil fertility, microbial ecology, and plant productivity, but also offer a climate-smart strategy for sustainable agriculture and effective reclamation of degraded, metal-contaminated soils.

MICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Biochar's influence on soil microbial activity plays a crucial role in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. By enhancing microbial processes, biochar not only supports soil health but also mitigates the emissions of potent GHGs such as N₂O and CH₄. Bai et al. (2025) reported a reduction in N₂O emissions, which was attributed to a significant increase in *amoA* (39.4%) and *nosZ* (41.7%) genes, alongside a

17.9% decrease in the *nirS* gene ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that biochar may enhance nitrification and denitrification by altering the microbial community structure and activity (Harter et al., 2014; Xiao et al., 2019). However, while biochar stimulates microbial activity, leading to increased CO₂ emissions, it simultaneously promotes CH₄ consumption by methanotrophic bacteria. This is reflected in a decreased *mcrA/pmoA* gene ratio, which favors methane oxidation over production (Zhao et al., 2024). Given the higher global warming potential of N₂O and CH₄ compared to CO₂, this mitigation effect outweighs the impact of elevated CO₂ emissions, ultimately contributing to greenhouse gas reduction (Bai et al., 2025). Kerner et al. (2023) conducted a three-level meta-analysis synthesizing 3899 observations of 24 microbial responses from 61 primary studies worldwide and reported that biochar significantly boosts microbial abundance in soil and increases the potential nitrification rate by 40.8%, while reducing cumulative N₂O emissions by 12.7% (increased *nirS* 8.2% and *nosZ* 7.4%); however, it increased cumulative CO₂ by 22.4%. Atilano-Camino et al. (2022) reported an increase in accumulated soil CO₂ emissions by 52.35% in the presence of microbial activity, while N₂O emissions significantly decreased by 32.23%.

Biochar application significantly alters soil microbial communities, influencing both diversity and functional potential. Deshoux et al. (2023) emphasized in their meta-analysis the critical role of biochar feedstock type in shaping microbial responses. Plant residue-derived biochars promoted the highest microbial biomass, sewage sludge biochars enhanced prokaryotic richness, and wood-derived biochars favored fungal diversity—attributed to differences in ash content, nutrient availability, and pore structure. High ash biochars (>40%) contributed more nutrients, promoting microbial growth, while woody biochars, with low nutrient content and high C/N ratios, generally suppressed microbial biomass but supported fungi via large, cylindrical pores. Soil texture and carbon content further influenced outcomes: microbial diversity was higher in medium- and coarse-textured soils for bacteria, and fine-textured soils for fungi. Biochars prepared at lower pyrolysis temperatures (<500 °C) were more effective in enhancing microbial diversity – these findings agreed to the findings of previous meta-analyses by Singh et al., 2022; Li et al., 2020. Furthermore, biochar had more pronounced effects in acidic and low-SOC soils, due to its liming effect and ability to stimulate native SOC mineralization. Application rate also shaped microbial dynamics differently - higher doses tended to reduce prokaryotic diversity but enhance fungal diversity, with the optimal dose for microbial stimulation reported as approximately 50.4 t·ha⁻¹.

Complementing these findings, a global meta-analysis by Xu et al. (2023) highlighted shifts in dominant bacterial phyla, where *Acidobacteria*, associated with biopolymer degradation and exopolysaccharide production (Kalam et al., 2020), declined under high biochar doses. In contrast, *Gemmatimonadetes*, known for rhizosphere carbon cycling, increased, particularly in drier or clay-rich soils where biochar improved water retention and porosity (Fawaz, 2013; Whitman et al., 2016). These changes were modulated by both application rate and soil properties; for instance, *Acidobacteria* were more sensitive to biochar dosage, while *Gemmatimonadetes* favored high C/N environments. Additionally, bacterial richness, as measured by Chao1 and OTU indices, increased with rising soil pH and biochar load. However, Shannon diversity remained stable, suggesting an increase in species richness but not evenness. Biochar also led to higher gram-positive bacterial biomass, possibly due to the provision of labile carbon and protective microhabitats (Luo et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2014). Furthermore, the rise in Chao1 diversity under biochar treatments was linked to broader carbon substrate utilization, suggesting that a richer microbial gene pool enables more efficient carbon metabolism. This functional

complementarity, e.g., Acidobacteria decomposing complex carbon and Gemmatimonadetes aiding rhizosphere interactions, may be a key mechanism by which biochar enhances soil health and resilience.

Application Information and Outcomes

HOW TO CHOOSE A BIOCHAR TYPE

Biochar selection should be done with the land manager's primary goals of biochar application in mind. In addition to the primary goal of increasing soil C stocks, biochar has a multitude of other potential benefits, including improved soil health and increasing crop yields and system sustainability. Biochar in general works very well to build soil C when the starting amount of soil C is relatively low, but biochar application can also significantly increase soil C in systems with initially relatively high (>1.5%) soil C stocks.

When selecting a biochar for a specific location, many factors should play a role in the selection process, including soil texture, current soil health and fertility status, cropping system and management practices. There is not one recommendation for biochar that fits all situations and locations, and in many cases, biochar may not be an appropriate amendment. It is important to use the large amount of scientific information that has been collected over the last decade to help guide selection of biochar based on the biochar properties needed to achieve desired outcomes in a specific context. This is also true for application rates, application method and timing.

BIOCHAR CRITERIA FOR IMPROVING SOIL PH AND REDUCING SALINITY

Biochar can be applied to acidic or alkaline soils, with appropriate consideration of the biochar pH prior to application. To increase soil pH where soil acidity is a problem, choose a biochar with a relatively high liming potential (i.e. $\geq 12\%$ CaCO₃ equivalent), which is generally a high temperature (> 500°C), high ash content biochar produced from base cation rich feedstocks, such as rice husks or corn stover. In alkaline, saline soils, biochar application can reduce the sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) and the exchangeable sodium percentage. To reduce alkaline pH and/or reduce negative impacts of salinity, choose an acidic biochar that has been produced through oxidation, hydrolysis, or acidification at moderate temperatures (400–500°C) to enhance CEC and porosity. In alkaline and saline soils, biochar produced from crop residues had the greatest positive impacts.

A somewhat alkaline pH biochar can be added to alkaline soils if the biochar also has a high CEC because these highly reactive (high CEC) biochars weather quickly such that an initial increase in pH just after application will disappear in weeks to months after application. If soils are highly acidic or alkaline, biochar alone may not be sufficient for adjusting soil to the ideal pH. Biochar degrades faster in acidic compared to alkaline soils, and the Ca⁺ usually present in alkaline soils promote mineral-organic matter complex formation, which stabilizes biochar and enhances soil C accrual.

BIOCHAR CRITERIA FOR IMPROVING WATER HOLDING CAPACITY AND SOIL STRUCTURE

Biochar can be applied to improve soil structure, which can help alleviate some of the negative impacts of drought or flooding. Most biochar types will have some positive impacts on soil structure, but biochar prepared at higher pyrolytic temperatures (>500 °C) can improve bulk density and porosity to a greater extent. In addition, biochar will generally improve soil aggregation, with the best results obtained from wood biochar with higher pyrolysis temperature (>600 °C). Manure-based biochar can better enhance soil water holding capacity (WHC) and can provide added resilience against flood stress. Soil WHC is most impacted by application of biochar with fine compared to coarse particle size and biochar with C content of < 50% compared to biochar with a C content > 70%. Biochar produced from crop residues (e.g., straw-based biochar) improves porosity and nutrient retention, reducing nutrient leaching in sandy flood deposits. Hardwood biochar offers long-term stability and helps immobilize contaminants, while waste biomass biochar provides a cost-effective solution for farmers.

CONSIDERATIONS FOR IMPROVING WATER HOLDING CAPACITY AND SOIL STRUCTURE

Overall, biochar not only improves soil WHC and bulk density and reduces compaction, but also supports the restoration of flood-damaged soils, highlighting its broad applicability as a soil amendment for enhancing soil structure and soil water retention across various soil types. In general, biochar is most effective improving soil structure in sandy to loamy textured soils, especially improving WHC. Biochar can reduce soil compaction by 3–31%, with a more substantial impact in coarse-textured soils such as sandy soils (~31% reduction) compared to finer-textured soils like clay (~9.2% reduction). Increases in WHC in biochar-amended sandy soils is most pronounced in soils with the highest sand content, acidic pH, and low C content.

BIOCHAR CRITERIA IMPROVE SOIL CEC AND NUTRIENT RETENTION AND PROVISIONING

Biochar generally increases CEC and can improve nutrient retention in both acidic and alkaline/saline soils; however, these effects vary significantly depending on management conditions, soil properties, biochar pyrolysis conditions, and biochar properties. If improvement of CEC and nutrient retention is a priority, the selection of a biochar is not generalizable and must be done after consideration of the specific soil type and management conditions using available literature.

CONSIDERATIONS FOR IMPROVING SOIL CEC AND NUTRIENT RETENTION AND PROVISIONING

Use of biochar as a soil amendment can significantly alter soil chemical properties and the direction and magnitude of these effects varies widely, depending on experimental duration, soil texture, initial soil pH, biochar pyrolysis conditions, biochar pH, and the biochar application rate.

COMPOST-BIOCHAR CO-APPLICATION CONSIDERATIONS

Compost-biochar co-application consistently improves soil health and fertility with positive impacts on crop yields, especially cereal crops. Co-composted biochar functions as a slow-release fertilizer that enhances nutrient availability, can reduce nutrient leaching, and restore degraded soils. There are three primary approaches for producing or co-applying biochar and compost: (i) co-composted biochar, produced by composting biochar with organic waste feedstocks; (ii) incubated biochar-compost, formed by incubating biochar with stabilized or mature compost over a specified period; and (iii) biochar-

compost mix, created by simply blending biochar and compost and applying it directly to soil. The addition of straw or woody biochars at a rate of 10–15% to compost is recommended due to its greater potential to both improve quality of compost and reduce its ecological risk by retaining nutrients in the soil. A wide range of compost-biochar application rates, from < 20 to > 30 t/ha, have been found to improve soil fertility and increase crop yields from 16-48%. The benefits of compost-biochar application are well-documented. Biochar and compost individually improve soil health through distinct mechanisms—biochar by enhancing soil structure, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and contaminant binding, and compost by improving fertility and stimulating microbial activity. Their combination provides all these benefits over and above what is seen with either biochar or compost alone, offering a more comprehensive improvement in soil health.

HOW MUCH BIOCHAR TO APPLY

In a global modelling study, He et al., 2024 developed recommendations for biochar application rates to reduce N emissions based on biochar and local soil properties and climate. They categorized biochar in to several categories including a low pH and low C content (LL-biochar), a low pH and high C content (LH-biochar), a high pH and low C content (HL-biochar), and a high pH and high C content (HH-biochar). In their analysis they determined that optimal strategy for both improving crop yields while also reducing N emissions, they recommended 40–80 t ha⁻¹ LL-biochar be applied in arid and sub-tropical regions and 0–20 t ha⁻¹ HL-biochar be applied in temperate regions (He et al., 2024). These application rates can be used as a starting point, but again the emphasis should be first on desired outcomes of biochar application and then selection of application rates that are ideal for those goals and that make sense financially.

Summary

Biochar is increasingly recognized as a versatile amendment for enhancing soil health and mitigating climate change. Its properties vary widely depending on feedstock and production conditions, influencing its stability, nutrient content, pH, and environmental impact. When applied to soils, biochar can significantly sequester carbon, reduce greenhouse gas emissions—especially nitrous oxide—and enhance crop yields by improving soil fertility, water retention, pH buffering, and microbial activity. These benefits are highly context-dependent, influenced by soil type, climate, cropping system, and application rates. While biochar's climate mitigation potential is largely derived from stabilizing biomass carbon and reducing N₂O emissions, careful attention must be paid to feedstock sourcing, production methods, and life cycle tradeoffs. Optimal outcomes require tailored biochar selection based on specific goals—such as improving water holding capacity, reducing soil compaction, increasing cation exchange capacity, or reclaiming saline soils—and local soil and environmental conditions. Integrated strategies, such as combining biochar with compost, further enhance its benefits, supporting a systems-based approach to sustainable soil and climate management.

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